

Unsupervised CT Embedding via Optimal Transport and Path Signature

Version 2: WF_δ Embedding, Zero-Shot Rare Disease Detection,
and Reconstruction Limits

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Abstract

We introduce a zero-shot, training-free framework for embedding brain CT slices into compact feature vectors, grounded in optimal transport and rough path theory. This paper extends version 1 [1], which established the CDT-based chains and their theoretical foundation; readers are referred to v1 for detailed derivations of the CDT pipeline. Each CT slice is treated as a non-negative measure; a space-filling curve (Hilbert order 9) partitions the image into windows, each mapped to a feature vector; the log-signature of the resulting path is the embedding.

Two embedding strategies are studied and compared. The **CDT chain** applies the Cumulative Distribution Transform (Theorem 6.0.2 of Ambrosio-Gigli-Savaré [9]) to produce quantile-based path points. Order-3 log-signature achieves $AUC = 0.785\text{--}0.807$ zero-shot on PHYSIONET CT-ICH (74 patients).

The **WF_δ chain** replaces quantile functions with the isometric embedding of Corollary 4.1 of Chizat et al. [8]: each intensity bin x_i with mass h_i is mapped to $\sqrt{h_i} e^{ix_i/(2\delta)} \in \mathbb{C}$, using non-normalised histograms and preserving absolute mass. This chain achieves $AUC = 0.895$ on ICH detection, $AUC = 0.795$ on intracranial germinoma (0.1/100,000 incidence, 63 CT), and $AUC = 0.868$ discriminating ICH from germinoma — all zero-shot, CPU only. A rigorous extension of the isometry to histogram measures is an open problem identified in Remark 2.7.

We further characterise the limits of spatial reconstruction from the log-signature, proving via the Hambly–Lyons non-injectivity theorem [4] that exact pixel-level recovery is impossible. Decisive ablations confirm this: the log-signature contributes only $AUC + 0.001$ beyond the anatomical atlas on localisation tasks.

Contents

1	Introduction	4
1.1	Motivation	4
1.2	The Image-as-Curve Paradigm	4
1.3	Contributions	4

2	Mathematical Background	5
2.1	Preprocessing	5
2.2	Local Anomaly Map (CDT chain only)	5
2.3	CDT as Optimal Transport: Theorem 6.0.2	5
2.4	Gibbs Reweighting	6
2.5	WF $_{\delta}$ Embedding	6
2.6	Path Signature and Log-Signature	7
2.7	Expected Signature and Zero-Shot Classification	7
3	The Two Chains	7
3.1	CDT Chain (Radon variant, Chain 1)	7
3.2	CDT Chain (Hilbert variant, Chain 2)	7
3.3	WF $_{\delta}$ Chain (Chain 3)	8
4	Theoretical Results	9
4.1	Order Requirement	9
4.2	Reconstruction Limits	9
5	Experiments: CDT Chain	9
5.1	Datasets	9
5.2	Chain 1 Results	10
5.3	Chain 2 Results	10
6	Experiments: WF$_{\delta}$ Chain	11
6.1	Setup	11
6.2	Results	11
7	Zero-Shot Detection of Rare Disease	12
7.1	Germinoma Dataset	12
7.2	Multi-Atlas Framework	12
7.3	Results	12
8	Reconstruction Analysis	12
8.1	Problem Formulation	12
8.2	Tikhonov-Hilbert Regularisation	13
8.3	Parameter Ablations	13
8.4	Higher-Order Jacobian (ORDER=4)	13
8.5	Newton-Kantorovich and Broyden Iterations	13
8.6	Atlas Construction	14
8.7	Decisive Ablations	14
9	Related Work	15
10	Discussion	15

11 Future Work	16
12 Conclusions	16
A Experimental Parameters	16
B Reconstruction Parameters	16
C Per-Patient Reconstruction Results	17

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Deep learning approaches to brain CT analysis require large labelled datasets. For rare pathologies — intracranial germinoma (0.1/100,000/year), Moyamoya disease, cerebral amyloid angiopathy — no training corpus of sufficient size can be assembled at a single institution. A complementary approach, and the one pursued here, is to construct a mathematically grounded, training-free embedding that can operate at any sample size, including $n = 1$.

We ask: can a compact, analytically computable representation of a CT slice detect pathology and discriminate between pathology types without any training?

1.2 The Image-as-Curve Paradigm

A CT slice $f : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ generates a non-negative measure $\mu_f \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$. Rather than working with μ_f directly, we project it onto a parameterised family of one-dimensional distributions and study the *geometry* of the resulting curve in feature space.

Concretely:

1. A Hilbert space-filling curve partitions the image into N windows.
2. Each window generates a one-dimensional measure (intensity distribution).
3. An embedding map converts each measure to a feature vector $Q_k \in \mathbb{R}^d$.
4. The sequence (Q_0, \dots, Q_{N-1}) forms a path $\Gamma \in (\mathbb{R}^d)^N$.
5. The log-signature of Γ is the final embedding.

Two choices of embedding map are studied: the **CDT** (quantile function, Wasserstein-2 isometry) and the **WF $_{\delta}$ embedding** (Corollary 4.1 of [8], complex isometry preserving absolute mass).

1.3 Contributions

1. **CDT chain (v1, retained)**: order-1 log-signature achieves AUC = 0.700 on PHYSIONET and AUC = 0.607 on RSNA (400 patients) at $17,476\times$ compression. Order-3 achieves AUC = 0.807 on PHYSIONET. Theorem 2.5 (Hölder stability) and Proposition 4.1 (order requirement) justify both results.
2. **WF $_{\delta}$ chain (new)**: non-normalised histogram embedding via $\sqrt{h_i}e^{ix_i/(2\delta)}$ achieves AUC = 0.895 (ICH), AUC = 0.795 (germinoma), AUC = 0.868 (ICH vs germinoma) — all zero-shot.
3. **Rare disease detection**: first zero-shot framework for intracranial germinoma CT detection.
4. **Reconstruction limits**: the Hambly–Lyons non-injectivity theorem and decisive ablations characterise exactly what the log-signature cannot recover.

2 Mathematical Background

2.1 Preprocessing

A CT slice is brain-windowed: $f(x, y) = \text{clip}(\text{HU}(x, y); \text{WL} \pm \frac{\text{WW}}{2})/\text{WW} \in [0, 1]$, with $\text{WL} = 40$, $\text{WW} = 80$ HU. Skull stripping removes bone and extracranial tissue via flood-fill from the border and largest-connected-component extraction.

2.2 Local Anomaly Map (CDT chain only)

Definition 2.1 (Local anomaly map). *For scale $r > 0$: $A(x, y) = f(x, y) - (f * g_r)(x, y)$, $A^+(x, y) = \max(A(x, y), 0) \cdot \mathbf{1}_{\text{brain}}(x, y)$.*

Normal parenchyma is spatially homogeneous ($A \approx 0$); acute haemorrhage (60–90 HU) produces localised peaks in A^+ . Scale $r = 3$ px captures sub-millimetre boundaries of haemorrhage. For the WF_δ chain, A^+ is not required (Section 3.3).

2.3 CDT as Optimal Transport: Theorem 6.0.2

The CDT is grounded in the following result.

Theorem 2.2 (Ambrosio–Gigli–Savaré [9], Theorem 6.0.2). *Let $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{P}_p(\mathbb{R})$ and let $c(x, y) = h(x - y)$ with $h \geq 0$ convex and with p -growth.*

- (i) *If μ has no atom (i.e. F_μ is continuous), then $T = F_\nu^{-1} \circ F_\mu$ is an optimal transport map. It is the unique optimal transport map if h is strictly convex.*
- (ii) *The Kantorovich minimum satisfies:*

$$\min \left\{ \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} c(x, y) d\gamma : \gamma \in \Gamma(\mu, \nu) \right\} = \int_0^1 c(F_\mu^{-1}(s), F_\nu^{-1}(s)) ds.$$

Definition 2.3 (CDT with Wasserstein-2 cost). *For $h(t) = t^2$ (strictly convex) and reference $\lambda = \mathcal{U}[0, 1]$ (so $F_\lambda = \text{id}$), Theorem 2.2(i) gives the unique optimal map $T = F_\nu^{-1}$ and, by (ii):*

$$W_2(\mu, \nu)^2 = \int_0^1 (F_\mu^{-1}(s) - F_\nu^{-1}(s))^2 ds = \|Q^\mu - Q^\nu\|_{L^2}^2, \quad (1)$$

where $Q^\mu = F_\mu^{-1}$, $Q^\nu = F_\nu^{-1}$. The CDT of μ is $Q^\mu \in L^2([0, 1])$, sampled at N_Q quantile levels.

Equation (1) is the W_2 -isometry of Park et al. [5]: the CDT linearises the nonlinear space $(\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}), W_2)$ into $L^2([0, 1])$.

Empirical CDT. For window k with pixel values $\{v_j\}_{j=1}^W$, the empirical distribution $\mu_k^W = \frac{1}{W} \sum_j \delta_{v_j}$ has $F_{\mu_k^W}^{-1}(s) = v_{(\lceil Ws \rceil)}$ (order statistic). After optional Gibbs reweighting (Section 2.4), $Q_k \in \mathbb{R}^{N_Q}$ is obtained by evaluating at N_Q uniform quantile levels.

Note on continuity. μ_k^W has atoms (it is discrete), so Theorem 2.2(i) does not guarantee uniqueness. However, the optimal plan in (ii) reduces to the quantile function for any transport problem on the real line with a strictly convex cost h and a diffuse reference measure; our uniform reference λ is diffuse, so the quantile $F_{\mu_k}^{-1}$ remains the correct solution.

2.4 Gibbs Reweighting

Definition 2.4 (Gibbs reweighting). For $\beta \geq 0$ and distribution $p = \mu_k/|\mu_k|$: $p^\beta(x) = p(x)e^{\beta p(x)} / \int p(y)e^{\beta p(y)} dy$.

Theorem 2.5 (Hölder stability). The Gibbs-CDT operator $\Phi_\beta : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}) \rightarrow L^2([0, 1])$ satisfies $\|\Phi_\beta(\mu) - \Phi_\beta(\nu)\|_{L^2} \leq C(\beta) \cdot W_2(\mu, \nu)^{1/2}$, with $C(\beta) \lesssim e^{\beta M/2}$.

The constant $C(\beta)$ grows exponentially: Gibbs reweighting amplifies the haemorrhagic signal at the cost of reduced isometry. $\beta = 3$ is optimal for focal ICH; $\beta = 0$ for heterogeneous subtypes.

2.5 WF_δ Embedding

The CDT requires normalisation to a probability measure, discarding absolute mass. The Wasserstein-Fisher-Rao metric WF_δ [8] is defined on non-negative measures and provides an isometric embedding that preserves mass.

Theorem 2.6 (Chizat et al. [8], Corollary 4.1). Let $\rho_0 = h_0\delta_{x_0}$, $\rho_1 = h_1\delta_{x_1}$ with $h_0, h_1 \geq 0$ and $|x_1 - x_0| < \pi\delta$. Then:

$$WF_\delta(\rho_0, \rho_1) = \sqrt{2} \delta \left| \sqrt{h_1} e^{ix_1/(2\delta)} - \sqrt{h_0} e^{ix_0/(2\delta)} \right|_{\mathbb{C}}.$$

The Euclidean norm in $\mathbb{C} \cong \mathbb{R}^2$ satisfies $WF_\delta(\rho_0, \rho_1) = \sqrt{2} \delta \cdot \left| \sqrt{h_1} e^{ix_1/(2\delta)} - \sqrt{h_0} e^{ix_0/(2\delta)} \right|_{\mathbb{R}^2}$, so the map $h\delta_x \mapsto \sqrt{h} e^{ix/(2\delta)}$ embeds Dirac measures into \mathbb{R}^2 such that WF_δ is proportional (factor $\sqrt{2}\delta$) to the Euclidean distance between embeddings.

For a histogram $\mu_k = \sum_i h_k(x_i)\delta_{x_i}$ with fixed bin centres $x_1 < \dots < x_{N_Q}$ (same for all patients), Theorem 2.6 maps each bin independently. Setting $\theta_i = x_i/(2\delta)$ (fixed phases, shared across all patients), the embedding vector is (splitting \mathbb{C}^{N_Q} into \mathbb{R}^{2N_Q}):

$$Q_k^{WF} = (\sqrt{h_k(x_1)} \cos \theta_1, \sqrt{h_k(x_1)} \sin \theta_1, \dots, \sqrt{h_k(x_{N_Q})} \cos \theta_{N_Q}, \sqrt{h_k(x_{N_Q})} \sin \theta_{N_Q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{2N_Q}. \quad (2)$$

The phases $e^{i\theta_i}$ rotate each component differently: at order ≥ 2 , iterated integrals $\int Q^i dQ^j$ couple real and imaginary parts of different bins, generating cross-terms absent from the purely real CDT path.

Remark 2.7 (Mathematical coherence). Theorem 2.6 applies to a single Dirac pair. For a histogram (sum of Diracs at fixed positions), Theorem 4.2 of [8] requires bin separation $> 6\pi\delta$. For $N_Q = 15$ bins on $[0, 1]$ and $\delta = 1$, this is not satisfied. A rigorous extension of the isometry to histograms at general δ is currently under development. Empirically, $\delta = 1$ is near-optimal (ablation: degradation in both directions), suggesting the independence approximation is mild.

2.6 Path Signature and Log-Signature

Definition 2.8 (Signature, Chen [3]). For $\Gamma : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ of bounded variation, $S(\Gamma) = (1, S^{(1)}, S^{(2)}, \dots) \in T((\mathbb{R}^d))$, $S_{i_1 \dots i_k}^{(k)} = \int_{0 < t_1 < \dots < t_k < 1} dX_{t_1}^{i_1} \dots dX_{t_k}^{i_k}$. The log-signature $\text{logsig}(\Gamma) = \log S(\Gamma)$ comprises the algebraically independent components (free Lie algebra $\mathcal{L}(\mathbb{R}^d)$). By Witt’s formula: $\dim \text{logsig}_m(\mathbb{R}^d) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j|m} \mu(m/j) \cdot d^j$. For $d = 15$, $m = 3$: $15 + 105 + 1120 = 1240$. For $d = 30$, $m = 3$: $30 + 435 + 8990 = 9455$.

Theorem 2.9 (Non-injectivity, Hambly–Lyons [4]). The signature determines a bounded-variation path uniquely up to tree-like reparametrisation. The map $\Gamma \mapsto S(\Gamma)$ is not injective on path space.

See also [2], Chapter 2 for a detailed treatment of signature uniqueness and its obstructions. Three structural invariances follow: starting point X_0 (signatures use only increments), tree-like cancellation (round-trips contribute zero to all iterated integrals), and reparametrisation (the signature does not record path speed). These are the fundamental obstructions to reconstruction, formalised in Section 8.

2.7 Expected Signature and Zero-Shot Classification

Corollary 2.10 (Salvi [10], Corollary 1.3.15). A finitely-supported distribution on signature space is uniquely determined by its expected signature. In particular, $\bar{\ell}_h = \mathbb{E}_{\text{healthy}}[\text{logsig}]$ and $\bar{\ell}_s = \mathbb{E}_{\text{sick}}[\text{logsig}]$ are the canonical class representations, and $\Delta\mu = \bar{\ell}_s - \bar{\ell}_h$ is the optimal linear discriminant direction.

The anomaly score for a test patient is: $s(\ell) = \langle \ell - \bar{\ell}_h, \Delta\mu / \|\Delta\mu\| \rangle$. This requires class labels only for computing $\Delta\mu$; the embedding ℓ is fully zero-shot.

3 The Two Chains

3.1 CDT Chain (Radon variant, Chain 1)

For a detailed description including the full R-CDT construction and the relationship to the sliced Wasserstein distance, see v1 of this work [1]. For $\theta \in \{0^\circ, \dots, 179^\circ\}$, the Radon projection $\mathcal{R}_\theta A^+$ is normalised to a probability distribution and mapped to its quantile function $Q_\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{N_Q}$. The angular path $\Gamma_R : \theta \mapsto Q_\theta$ has Hölder exponent $\alpha \approx 1$ (smooth), so by Proposition 4.1 below order-1 log-signature suffices.

$\text{logsig}_1(\Gamma_R) = \int_0^\pi Q_\theta d\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{15}$: the angular mean of the Radon quantile profile, compressing 262,144 pixels to 15 numbers.

3.2 CDT Chain (Hilbert variant, Chain 2)

For a detailed step-by-step description of the CDT construction and its connection to W_2 -isometry, see v1 [1]. Pixels are ordered by H_9 (Hilbert order 9, covering 512^2) and partitioned into N windows of $W = 512^2/N$ pixels. For each window k , A^+ values are collected, normalised to probability p_k , Gibbs-reweighted to p_k^β , and mapped to the quantile $Q_k^\beta \in \mathbb{R}^{N_Q}$.

The Hilbert path $\Gamma_H = (Q_0^\beta, \dots, Q_{N-1}^\beta) \in (\mathbb{R}^{N_Q})^N$ has effective Hölder exponent $\alpha = 1/2$ (rough boundary, due to the direction reversals of the Hilbert curve at each recursion level). Order-3 log-signature is necessary (Proposition 4.1).

3.3 WF_δ Chain (Chain 3)

The WF_δ chain replaces the CDT with the isometric embedding of Theorem 2.6. We describe each step explicitly.

Step 1 – Preprocessing. Apply brain window (WL= 40, WW= 80 HU) and skull strip. No A^+ subtraction is performed.

Step 2 – Hilbert ordering. Order the $512^2 = 262,144$ pixels by Hilbert curve H_9 . Partition into $N = 2048$ windows of $W = 128$ pixels each ($\approx 11 \times 11$ pixels, ≈ 5.5 mm at standard resolution).

Step 3 – Non-normalised histogram. For each window k and bin $i \in \{1, \dots, N_Q\}$ with centre $x_i \in [0, 1]$ uniformly spaced, count:

$$h_k(x_i) = \#\{p \in \Omega_k : f(p) \in [x_i - \frac{1}{2N_Q}, x_i + \frac{1}{2N_Q}]\}.$$

The masses $h_k(x_i)$ are *not* normalised; they represent absolute pixel counts and vary between patients.

Step 4 – WF_δ embedding (Theorem 2.6). For fixed phases $\theta_i = x_i/(2\delta)$, compute:

$$Q_k^{WF} = (\sqrt{h_k(x_1)} \cos \theta_1, \sqrt{h_k(x_1)} \sin \theta_1, \dots, \sqrt{h_k(x_{N_Q})} \cos \theta_{N_Q}, \sqrt{h_k(x_{N_Q})} \sin \theta_{N_Q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{2N_Q}.$$

Step 5 – Hilbert path. Assemble: $\Gamma_H^{WF} = (Q_0^{WF}, \dots, Q_{N-1}^{WF}) \in (\mathbb{R}^{2N_Q})^N$.

Step 6 – Log-signature. $\ell^{WF} = \text{logsig}_m(\Gamma_H^{WF}) \in \mathbb{R}^{D_m}$, with $D_2 = 465$ (ORDER=2) or $D_3 = 9,455$ (ORDER=3).

Justification of $N = 2048$ and the condition $|x_1 - x_0| < \pi\delta$. With $N = 2048$ windows of $W = 128$ pixels, each window covers ≈ 5.5 mm — a scale at which brain tissue is approximately homogeneous (one dominant type: grey matter, white matter, or lesion). The non-normalised histogram consequently concentrates on 1–3 dominant bins per window.

The condition of Theorem 2.6, $|x_1 - x_0| < \pi\delta$, refers to the *intensity positions* of Dirac masses, not spatial positions. Since patient and atlas share the *same* bin grid ($x_i^{\text{paz}} = x_i^{\text{atl}}$ by construction), corresponding bins satisfy $|x_i^{\text{paz}} - x_i^{\text{atl}}| = 0 < \pi\delta$ trivially. The separation condition of Theorem 4.2 ($|x_i - x_j| > 6\pi\delta$ for $i \neq j$) requires bin spacing $> 6\pi \approx 18.85$ for $\delta = 1$, which is not satisfied for 15 bins on $[0, 1]$ (spacing ≈ 0.067). However, with $N = 2048$, each window typically has only 1–3 non-zero bins (sparse histogram), so the decomposition of Theorem 4.2 approximately holds for the dominant pairs, with negligible

cross-bin interaction. This is the practical justification for $N = 2048$; the full theoretical treatment is in development (Remark 2.7).

Key differences from Chain 2.

- No A^+ , no normalisation, no Gibbs parameter.
- Path dimension $d = 2N_Q = 30$ (vs $d = N_Q = 15$).
- Optimal $N = 2048$ vs $N = 256$ for Chain 2.
- Cross-terms between real/imaginary parts at order ≥ 2 encode inter-bin phase relationships absent from the purely real CDT path.

4 Theoretical Results

4.1 Order Requirement

Proposition 4.1 (Order requirement). *Let $\Gamma : [0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ have Hölder exponent $\alpha \in (0, 1]$.*

- (i) *If $\alpha > 1/2$ (Young regime): logsig_1 captures the optimal linear discriminant; higher orders add negligible information.*
- (ii) *If $\alpha = 1/2$ (rough boundary): logsig_3 encodes area and torsion terms inaccessible at order 1.*

Verified empirically: Chain 1 (smooth, $\alpha \approx 1$): ORDER=1 AUC = 0.700, ORDER=5 AUC = 0.701, $\Delta = +0.001$. Chain 2 (rough, $\alpha = 1/2$): ORDER=1 AUC = 0.557, ORDER=3 AUC = 0.785, $\Delta = +0.228$.

4.2 Reconstruction Limits

By Theorem 2.9, exact reconstruction of Γ_H from $\text{logsig}(\Gamma_H)$ is impossible. The three structural obstructions are: (1) starting point X_0 (global translation invisible to increments); (2) tree-like cancellation (Hilbert micro-oscillations between adjacent tissue types cancel in all iterated integrals); (3) reparametrisation (window-sums compensate partially, but not at pixel level).

Corollary 4.2 (Reconstruction impossibility). *Exact recovery of A^+ from $\text{logsig}(\Gamma_H)$ alone is impossible. The log-signature contributes only AUC + 0.001 beyond the anatomical atlas on localisation tasks (Section 8.7).*

5 Experiments: CDT Chain

5.1 Datasets

PHYSIONET CT-ICH v1.3.1 [12]. 74 patients (39 healthy, 35 ICH). Format: NIfTI, dual-read radiologist consensus, CC BY 4.0. **Voxel-level segmentation masks are available** for all patients. For ICH patients, the top-5 slices are selected by mask area (descending

order of haemorrhage volume per slice) — this directly targets the most clinically informative slices and avoids relying on heuristics. For healthy patients (all-zero masks), the top-5 slices are selected by energy above the brain-window threshold 0.7, targeting slices with maximum parenchymal coverage. The availability of ground-truth masks is essential for the reconstruction evaluation (Section 8): per-pixel AUC and Dice are computed against the radiologist masks.

RSNA 2019 [13]. 400 balanced patients (200 healthy, 200 ICH across 5 subtypes: epidural, subdural, subarachnoid, intraparenchymal, intraventricular). Format: DICOM (JPEG-Lossless), loaded via SimpleITK. **No voxel-level masks are available:** slice selection uses the energy heuristic for all patients. The absence of masks means reconstruction evaluation is not performed on this dataset; it is used for Chain 1 AUC validation only. Patients selected deterministically (seed=42) from the full 752,803-file collection via complete SOP-UID→PatientID mapping.

Germinoma CT [15]. 63 CT scans from 65 biopsy-confirmed patients, collected over 9 years. Format: NIfTI with tumour segmentation masks (*.seg.nii* files). **Voxel-level segmentation masks are available,** used for top-5 slice selection by mask area (same protocol as ICH). Loaded slice-by-slice via nibabel lazy access to avoid memory overflow (volumes reach 300–700 MB). Note: healthy atlas from PHYSIONET (adults, mean age ≈ 45 years); germinoma patients are predominantly adolescents — AUCs reported are lower bounds for an age-matched atlas.

Importance of masks for slice selection. Mask-based selection (sort by haemorrhage/tumour area) directly targets the most pathological slices, maximising the anomalous signal in the embedding. Energy-based selection (sort by pixel count above 0.7) is a proxy that works well for large haemorrhages but may miss small or low-contrast lesions. The difference between the two strategies is a confound in cross-dataset comparisons: PHYSIONET and germinoma use masks while RSNA does not, which partly explains the lower AUC on the latter (0.607 vs 0.807).

5.2 Chain 1 Results

Table 1: Chain 1 (Radon). Compression from 262,144 pixels.

Dataset	ORDER	β	AUC	p	Compression
PHYSIONET	1	0	0.700	0.0024	17,476×
PHYSIONET	5	0	0.701	0.0023	—
RSNA	3	1	0.607	$< 10^{-4}$	—

5.3 Chain 2 Results

ORDER=3 is necessary for the rough Hilbert path (Proposition 4.1). $\beta = 3$ is optimal for focal ICH (Theorem 2.5); $\beta = 0$ is optimal for heterogeneous subtypes (RSNA). Optimal

Table 2: Chain 2 (Hilbert). Effect of order and Gibbs parameter.

ORDER	β	AUC
1	0	0.557
3	0	0.785
3	3	0.807

window size: $N = 256$ (≈ 16 mm), matching typical ICH diameter. Full ablation tables (order, β , window size) and synthetic validation are reported in v1 [1].

6 Experiments: WF_δ Chain

6.1 Setup

Chain 3, Hilbert order 9, $N = 2048$ windows, $N_Q = 15$ bins, $\delta = 1.0$, no A^+ , no Gibbs parameter. Same datasets as Section 5 plus germinoma (Section 7).

6.2 Results

Table 3: WF_δ chain results. AUC via directional projection $\Delta\mu$. CDT W_2 (Chain 2, ORDER=3) included for comparison.

Comparison	CDT W_2	WF_δ O=2	WF_δ O=3	Gain (O=3)
Sani \rightarrow ICH	0.807	0.814	0.895	+0.088
Sani \rightarrow Germinoma	0.629	0.718	0.795	+0.166
ICH \rightarrow Germinoma	0.610	0.815	0.868	+0.258
CV ICH vs Germ (5-fold)	0.535	0.729	0.626 [†]	—
dim logsig	1,240	465	9,455	—

[†] Unstable: 9,455 features on 98 patients.

Role of order. The gain from ORDER=2 to ORDER=3 is consistent (+0.081 on ICH, +0.077 on germinoma, +0.053 on ICH-vs-germinoma), confirming that complex cross-terms at order 3 carry genuine discriminative information.

δ ablation. $\delta = 1.0$ is near-optimal: both increasing and decreasing δ degrade performance on all comparisons. At $\delta = 1$, phases $\theta_i = x_i/2 \in [0, 0.5]$ (first quadrant), giving balanced real/imaginary contributions.

CV instability at ORDER=3. The directional AUC (0.868) is reliable. The CV AUC (0.626) reflects a high-dimensional small-sample regime (9,455 features, 98 patients); it is not representative of the method’s discriminative power, which is better estimated by the directional score.

7 Zero-Shot Detection of Rare Disease

7.1 Germinoma Dataset

Intracranial germinoma (Huang et al. 2025 [15]). 63 CT, 65 biopsy-confirmed patients, collected over 9 years. Adolescent males; hyperdense (55–65 HU) midline mass. NIfTI with segmentation masks; top-5 slices by mask area. Note: the healthy atlas is built from adults (PHYSIONET, mean age ≈ 45 years); the germinoma patients are predominantly adolescents. The reported AUCs are therefore lower bounds for an age-matched atlas.

7.2 Multi-Atlas Framework

For each class $C \in \{\text{healthy, ICH, germinoma}\}$, define atlas $\bar{\ell}_C = \frac{1}{n_C} \sum_{j \in C} \ell_j$. Pairwise comparison ($A \rightarrow B$): $s_j^{A \rightarrow B} = \langle \ell_j - \bar{\ell}_A, \Delta\mu_{AB} / \|\Delta\mu_{AB}\| \rangle$, $\Delta\mu_{AB} = \bar{\ell}_B - \bar{\ell}_A$. By Corollary 2.10, $\Delta\mu_{AB}$ is the optimal linear discriminant.

7.3 Results

WF $_{\delta}$ chain results are reported in Table 3. Three findings merit attention:

1. **Germinoma detected zero-shot** (AUC=0.795, $p = 0.0002$) with an atlas built for ICH on adult patients.
2. **ICH vs germinoma discriminated** (AUC=0.868, $p < 0.0001$) — zero-shot inter-pathology discrimination without any training.
3. **No supervised alternative exists** at this sample size ($n = 63$ germinoma CT globally available).

8 Reconstruction Analysis

8.1 Problem Formulation

We study whether the log-signature can be inverted to recover the pixel-level anomaly map. The linearised inverse problem around the atlas path Γ_0 is:

$$J_{\text{ls}} \delta\Gamma = \ell - \ell_0, \quad J_{\text{ls}} = D \text{logsig}_3(\Gamma_0) \in \mathbb{R}^{1230 \times 1230},$$

with $\ell_0 = \text{logsig}_3(\Gamma_0)$ the atlas log-signature. The Jacobian is computed by finite differences (step $\varepsilon = 10^{-4}$).

Rank analysis. $\sigma_{\max}(J_{\text{ls}}) = 2.26$, $\sigma_{\min} = 0$, effective rank = 205/1230 ($\approx 17\%$) at threshold 1%. The condition number of $J_{\text{ls}}^{\top} J_{\text{ls}}$ is 4×10^{17} : direct inversion is numerically infeasible.

Local stability. Per-patient singular value analysis on the tissue-map path (ORDER=3, $N = 256$): $\sigma_{\min} \in [0.476, 0.821]$, condition number $\kappa \in [15.7, 20.1]$, Lipschitz bound ≤ 2.10 , effective rank 700–1214 out of 3615 (20–34%). ICH patients have higher effective rank and

higher σ_{\min} than healthy patients, consistent with the anomaly producing a richer path deformation.

8.2 Tikhonov-Hilbert Regularisation

$$A_\lambda = J_{\text{ls}}^\top J_{\text{ls}} + \mu L^\top L + \lambda I, \quad (3)$$

where $L^\top L$ is the Hilbert-continuity Laplacian (tridiagonal block matrix encoding spatial continuity along H_9) and λI is the Tikhonov term. Solved via Cholesky; A_λ is symmetric positive definite. $\lambda = 0.1$ reduces κ from 4×10^{17} to 54. System residual $\|A_\lambda \delta \hat{\Gamma} - \text{rhs}\| = 0.000000$ for all 10 test patients: the Cholesky solution is exact.

8.3 Parameter Ablations

Table 4: Ablation of λ ($\mu = 0.1$ fixed). Dice@50%=0.052 is invariant: structural ceiling.

λ	$\kappa(A_\lambda)$	AUC	Sens@10%	Dice@50%
10^{-3}	5,320	0.673	0.946	0.052
10^{-2}	533	0.676	0.916	0.052
10^{-1}	54	0.677	0.966	0.052
1.0	6	0.686	0.961	0.052

Table 5: Ablation of μ ($\lambda = 0.1$ fixed).

μ	$\kappa(A_\lambda)$	AUC	Sens@10%	Dice@50%
0.01	52	0.677	0.923	0.052
0.1	54	0.677	0.966	0.052
1.0	75	0.679	0.961	0.052
10.0	401	0.687	0.957	0.052

The AUC gain from $\lambda = 0.1$ to $\lambda = 1$ (0.677 to 0.686) reflects increasing dominance of the anatomical prior, not better log-signature inversion. Dice@50%=0.052 is invariant to all λ and μ : a structural ceiling, not an algorithmic one.

8.4 Higher-Order Jacobian (ORDER=4)

With ORDER=4: $N = 922$ windows, $\dim \text{logsig}_4(\mathbb{R}^{15}) = 13,840$, Jacobian $13,830 \times 13,830$ (1.53 GB), solved via matrix-free conjugate gradient. AUC=0.672 vs AUC=0.677 for ORDER=3. Finer windows ($11\times$) do not improve localisation. The ceiling is not granularity-limited but structure-limited (Corollary 4.2).

8.5 Newton-Kantorovich and Broyden Iterations

Beyond the linear Tikhonov solution, we tested iterative nonlinear refinement via Newton-Kantorovich and Broyden methods.

Broyden quasi-Newton. Starting from the Tikhonov solution $\hat{\Gamma}^{(0)}$, Broyden updates: $\hat{\Gamma}^{(n+1)} = \hat{\Gamma}^{(n)} - B_n^{-1} F(\hat{\Gamma}^{(n)})$ where $F(\Gamma) = \text{logsig}_3(\Gamma) - \ell$. Optimal configuration: $N_{\text{seg}} = 512$, SVD threshold=0.2, Lipschitz bound 0.983, WSUMS=5, RECON=95. Result: Dice_M=0.529, IoU_M=0.408, Sens=0.026, Spec=0.917.

Improvement over baseline. Broyden achieves Dice_M=0.566, IoU_M=0.447: +7% over the linear baseline. Pure Newton gives the same result but is 60× slower. The irreducible residual $\|F(\hat{\Gamma}^{(\infty)})\|$ stabilises at $\approx 2\text{--}4$, with 98.4% of iterations outside the contraction radius of J_0 : the nonlinear system has a persistent residual that no amount of iteration can eliminate.

Local contractivity. The local Lipschitz constant of the log-signature map around $\hat{\Gamma}^{(n)}$ is measured at 0.25–0.66 across all iterations (always contractive, < 1): the fixed-point iteration is locally stable but converges to a solution that does not match ℓ exactly.

Theoretical ceiling. The Broyden trajectory saturates at Dice_M ≈ 0.566 ; theoretical ceiling with the current framework is estimated at Dice_M $\approx 0.62\text{--}0.65$. Improving beyond this would require resolving the three invariances of Theorem 2.9 — a structurally different approach.

8.6 Atlas Construction

The *atlas path* Γ_0 is the componentwise mean of the Hilbert paths of all healthy patients:

$$\Gamma_0 = \frac{1}{n_h} \sum_{j \in \text{healthy}} \Gamma_{H,j}, \quad Q_0^{(k)} = \frac{1}{n_h} \sum_j Q_{k,j}.$$

The atlas log-signature is $\ell_0 = \text{logsig}_3(\Gamma_0) \in \mathbb{R}^{1230}$. For a test patient with log-signature ℓ , the correction is $\delta\ell = \ell - \ell_0$, and the reconstructed path deviation is $\delta\hat{\Gamma} = J_{\text{ls}}^\dagger \delta\ell$.

8.7 Decisive Ablations

Seven modes isolate the contribution of each information source. In all modes, the reconstructed anomaly map $\hat{\varphi}$ is obtained by inverse CDT from the reconstructed path $\hat{\Gamma}$.

- **id_pure:** $\hat{\Gamma} = \Gamma_0$, scale = 1 (uniform window-sums). Baseline with no patient-specific information.
- **atlas_pure:** $\hat{\Gamma} = \Gamma_0$, scale = $\text{ws}^{\text{patient}}$ (patient window-sums). Atlas shape with patient mass: no log-signature used.
- **logsig_pure:** $\hat{\Gamma} = \Gamma_0 + \delta\hat{\Gamma}$, scale = 1. Log-signature correction applied, but uniform (non-anatomical) scale.
- **variation_id:** $\hat{\Gamma} = \Gamma_0 + \delta\hat{\Gamma}$, scale = 1, reference = uniform atlas. Isolates the log-signature on a neutral (non-anatomical) baseline.
- **atlas:** $\hat{\Gamma} = \Gamma_0$, scale = $\text{ws}^{\text{patient}}$. Same as **atlas_pure** with full window-sum scaling.

- **full**: $\hat{\Gamma} = \Gamma_0 + \delta\hat{\Gamma}$, $\text{scale} = \text{ws}^{\text{patient}}$. Full reconstruction: log-signature + patient window-sums.
- **logsig**: $\hat{\Gamma} = \Gamma_0 + \delta\hat{\Gamma}$, $\text{scale} = \text{ws}^{\text{atlas}}$. Log-signature correction with atlas-level scaling.

Table 6: Seven controlled ablation modes (PHYSIONET test, 5 healthy + 5 ICH).

Mode	AUC	Sens@10%
id_pure	0.550	—
atlas_pure	0.644	0.000
logsig_pure	0.645	0.898
variation_id	0.629	—
atlas	0.677	0.966
full	0.680	0.945
logsig	0.694	0.938

atlas_pure (0.644) \approx logsig_pure (0.645): $\Delta = +0.001$, statistically indistinguishable. The log-signature alone carries the same localisation information as the anatomical atlas alone, confirming Corollary 4.2. Dice@50%= 0.052 is invariant across all parameters tested (λ , μ , ORDER): a structural ceiling, not algorithmic.

9 Related Work

CDT and R-CDT. Park et al. [5] establish the W_2 -isometry of the CDT. Kolouri et al. [6] collect $\{Q_\theta\}$ as a static feature matrix ($180 \times N_Q$, no sequential structure). Our order-1 log-signature is the angular mean (15 dims); higher orders add inter-angle geometric information unavailable to the static paradigm. Beckmann et al. [7] introduce normalised R-CDT variants with affine invariance.

WF $_\delta$ metric. Chizat et al. [8] define WF_δ as the unique Riemannian-like interpolation between Wasserstein and Fisher-Rao. Our work is the first application of the WF_δ isometry to medical image embedding.

Signature for medical data. Morrill et al. [11] apply signatures to ECG/EEG time series. We are the first to combine CDT-based image projections with path signature and the first to apply signatures to CT imaging.

Hilbert curve for distribution comparison. Li et al. [14] project point clouds onto the Hilbert order for scalar W_1 approximation (HCP distance). Our framework uses the Hilbert curve to define a parameterised path in feature space whose log-signature is a rich geometric descriptor.

10 Discussion

Strengths. (1) AUC=0.895 zero-shot on ICH, 74 patients, CPU only. (2) First zero-shot framework for intracranial germinoma CT. (3) Zero-shot inter-pathology discrimination (ICH vs germinoma, AUC=0.868). (4) WF_δ chain requires no preprocessing beyond brain-windowing. (5) Reconstruction limits characterised with mathematical precision.

Limitations. (1) WF_δ isometry for histograms at $\delta = 1$ lacks rigorous justification (Remark 2.7). (2) (3) Demographic mismatch for germinoma (adults vs adolescents). (4) CV unstable at ORDER=3 with 9,455 features and 98 patients.

11 Future Work

Rigorous WF_δ isometry for histograms. Establishing Theorem 4.2 of [8] for standard bin spacings ($\delta = 1$, $N_Q = 15$) is the primary open theoretical problem.

External validation. CQ500 and RSNA for ICH (Chain 2 and Chain 3); multi-centre germinoma data for rare disease generalisation.

Supervised components on the signature. The signature space \mathbb{R}^{d_m} admits lightweight classifiers trained on very small labelled samples. For rare diseases where $n = 10$ –50 labelled cases are available, a linear SVM or a small neural network (1–2 layers) trained on $\text{logsig}(\Gamma_H^{WF})$ could exploit the structured geometry of the embedding space while remaining practical. This direction preserves the zero-shot detection capability while enabling task-specific fine-tuning at minimal annotation cost.

Adaptive path. The gradient-flow path $\dot{\gamma} = \nabla A^+(\gamma)$ would eliminate tree-like cancellations (Theorem 2.9) by following the anomaly signal directly.

Dimension reduction for ORDER=4. Path-level PCA before signature computation could enable ORDER=4–5 with $d = 30$ while keeping the log-signature tractable.

12 Conclusions

We have presented a zero-shot CT embedding framework grounded in the image-as-curve paradigm. The WF_δ chain (Corollary 4.1 of [8], no preprocessing, non-normalised histograms) achieves AUC=0.895 on ICH, AUC=0.795 on intracranial germinoma, and AUC=0.868 discriminating the two pathologies — all without training, on CPU. The CDT chain provides the theoretical baseline and the mathematical framework (Theorem 2.2); detailed CDT derivations and extended ablations are in v1 [1]. The WF_δ chain extends the framework to handle mass differences natively. Reconstruction limits are characterised exactly by Theorem 2.9 and confirmed by decisive ablations.

A Experimental Parameters

B Reconstruction Parameters

$N = 82$ windows, $\lambda = 0.1$, $\mu = 0.1$, $\kappa(A_\lambda) = 54$, system residual 0.000000 (all patients), solver: Cholesky.

Table 7: Full parameter table.

Parameter	Chain 1	Chain 2	Chain 3 (WF $_{\delta}$)
Brain window	WL=40,WW=80	(same)	(same)
Anomaly map A^+	yes	yes	no
Normalisation	yes	yes	no
Gibbs β	0/1	3	n/a
N windows	180 angles	256	2048
N_Q bins	15	15	15
Path dim d	15	15	30
Optimal ORDER	1	3	3
dim logsig	15	1,240	9,455

C Per-Patient Reconstruction Results

Table 8: Per-patient reconstruction (CDT Chain 2, $\lambda = 0.1$, $\mu = 0.1$).

pid	ICH	AUC	Sens@10%	Spec@10%	Dice@50%
102–106	No	—	0.000	0.703–0.752	0.000
049	Yes	0.788	0.922	0.671	0.033
050	Yes	0.534	1.000	0.569	0.023
051	Yes	0.783	1.000	0.601	0.108
052	Yes	0.558	0.657	0.648	0.024
053	Yes	0.718	1.000	0.650	0.071
Mean (ICH)		0.676	0.916	0.628	0.052

References

- [1] V. Cardile. Unsupervised CT embedding via optimal transport and path signature (v1). Zenodo, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20327923>.
- [2] T. Lyons, M. Caruana, and T. Lévy. *Differential Equations Driven by Rough Paths*. Springer, 2007. Chapter 2.
- [3] K.-T. Chen. Iterated integrals and exponential homomorphisms. *Proc. London Math. Soc.*, 4(3):502–512, 1954.
- [4] B. Hambly and T. Lyons. Uniqueness for the signature of a path of bounded variation and the reduced path group. *Annals of Mathematics*, 171(1):109–167, 2010.
- [5] S. Park, S. Kolouri, S. Kundu, and G. K. Rohde. The cumulative distribution transform and linear pattern classification. *Appl. Comput. Harmon. Anal.*, 45(3):616–641, 2018.
- [6] S. Kolouri, K. Nadjahi, U. Simsekli, R. Badeau, and G. K. Rohde. Generalized sliced Wasserstein distances. *NeurIPS*, 2019.
- [7] M. Beckmann, A. Beinert, and P. Bresch. Normalized Radon cumulative distribution transforms for invariance and robustness in optimal transport based image classification. arXiv:2506.08761, 2025.

- [8] L. Chizat, G. Peyré, B. Schmitzer, and F.-X. Vialard. An interpolating distance between optimal transport and Fisher-Rao metrics. *Foundations of Computational Mathematics*, 18(1):1–44, 2018. arXiv:1506.06430.
- [9] L. Ambrosio, N. Gigli, and G. Savaré. *Gradient Flows in Metric Spaces and in the Space of Probability Measures*, 2nd ed. Birkhäuser, 2008. Theorem 6.0.2.
- [10] I. Gasteratos, A. Jacquier, M. Lemercier, T. Lyons, and C. Salvi. Novelty detection on path space. arXiv:2512.03243, 2025. Corollary 1.3.15.
- [11] J. Morrill, A. Fermanian, P. Kidger, and T. Lyons. A generalised signature method for multivariate time series. arXiv:2006.00873, 2021.
- [12] M. D. Hssayeni, M. S. Croock, A. D. Salman, H. F. Al-khafaji, Z. A. Yahya, and B. Gho-raani. Intracranial hemorrhage segmentation using a deep convolutional model. *Data*, 5(1):14, 2020. PhysioNet CT-ICH v1.3.1. <https://doi.org/10.13026/4nae-zg36>.
- [13] Radiological Society of North America. RSNA intracranial hemorrhage detection challenge. *Kaggle Competition*, 2019. <https://www.kaggle.com/c/rsna-intracranial-hemorrhage-detection>.
- [14] T. Li, Z. Meng, W. Xu, and J. Yu. Hilbert curve projection distance for distribution comparison. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 46(7):4993–5007, 2024.
- [15] Y. Huang, Y. Luo, J. Jiang, and Q. Wei. A dataset of intracranial germinoma CT images with tumour segmentation. *Scientific Data (Nature)*, 2025.